

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY FEATURES, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PYELONEPHRITIS IN CHILDREN DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7315437>

Abstract: At the turn of 2019-2020, humanity was affected by a new viral infection, SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19), which spread rapidly in many countries and reached pandemic proportions. It was found that 27.06% of hospitalised patients with coronavirus infection had kidney damage.

Objective of the study: to determine the clinical and laboratory features, early diagnosis of pyelonephritis during the COVID-19 pandemic in children and to evaluate the efficacy of comprehensive treatment.

Subject and object of study: Fifty patients with COVID-19 at the age of 2 to 15 years were recruited. Fifty children with pyelonephritis not infected with COVID-19 disease were taken as a control group.

Materials and Methods: 1. General clinical - history, pedigree analysis, examination, blood and urine tests.

2. instrumental - renal ultrasound with Dopplerometry, blood pressure measurement.

Results: The activity of the inflammatory process was assessed by the number of leukocytes, neutrophil granulocytes and erythrocyte sedimentation rate in peripheral blood. In 48 (96%) children of the first group sedimentation rate was registered from 17 to 38 mm/h, leukocytosis - from $13 \cdot 10^9$ to $35 \cdot 10^9$. In group 2 patients a sedimentation rate was relatively less frequently revealed - 22 (44%) ($p < 0,01$), neutrophilic leukocytosis - 6 (12%) ($p < 0,05$). The addition of vitamin A to the treatment regimen increased the efficacy of treatment by 15.4% ($R > 0,05$). The effect of vitamin A on treatment efficacy can be explained by improved metabolic processes in tissues, including the kidneys.

Conclusions: The pyelonephritis in children exposed to COVID-19 is characterized by predominant signs of intoxication. The high efficiency of treatment in the main group of patients was associated with the addition of the antihypoxant drug vitamin A to the treatment regimen, which not only had a

positive effect on the renal tubule epithelium but also improved the erythrocyte function.

